

OXIDATION OF AROMATIC THIOCARBAMIDES: ON THE CHEMISTRY AND STRUCTURE OF HUGERSHOFF'S AND HOFMANN AND GABRIEL'S THIODIAZOLES

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Hugershoff's base cannot be represented by the thiodiazole structure, initially assigned to it. An alternative structure, which is in better agreement with the facts, has been proposed. Hofmann and Gabriel's thiodiazole, however, appears to have the structure assigned to it. Its UV absorption spectrum shows marked agreement with that of 3:5-diphenylimino-1:2:4-thiodiazole, obtained by the oxidative cyclisation of *N*-phenylformamido-*N'*-phenylthiocarbamide.

By the bromine oxidation of thiocarbanilide in an alcoholic medium Hugershoff (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 3131) reported the formation of a base, $C_{26}H_{20}N_4S$, m.p. 136° , and assigned to it the structure of a thiodiazole (I). A similar thiodiazole base (II), $C_{18}H_{14}N_4S$, m.p. $93-94^\circ$, was reported to have been formed by the hydrogen peroxide oxidation of *NN*-methylphenylthiocarbamide in an alcoholic medium by Hofmann and Gabriel (*Ber.*, 1882, 28, 1578).

Although these structures appear to have received acceptance, no direct proof has yet been furnished for the thiodiazole hetero-ring system present in them.

Since (i) thiocarbanilide, *NN*-methylphenylthiocarbamide and other aromatic substituted thiocarbamides under certain conditions are oxidised easily to benzthiazoles (Hugershoff, *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 3121; Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2023, 2270, et seq; Dost, *Ber.*, 1906, 39, 1014; Sahasrabudhey and Krall, *this Journal*, 1944, 21, 17; Sahasrabudhey, *ibid.*, 1950, 27, 433; Allen and Allan, "Org. Syn.", 1942, Vol. 22, p. 16; Mukherjee and Suresh, *J. V'k. Univ.*, 1958, II, 127) and (ii) it has been shown by the author (*this Journal*, 1958, 35, 170) that the reported thiodiazoles from certain diaryl-substituted thiocarbamides (De and Chakravarty, *ibid.*, 1928, 5, 661) are not thiodiazoles at all, a reinvestigation of the chemistry of the above two compounds is not without interest.

Hugershoff's Base

Fromm and Bitterich (*Annalen*, 1912, 394, 284) have reported that Hugershoff's above base, (i) when heated* with hydrochloric and acetic acids, furnished triphenylguanidine, aniline, sulphur and 2-phenylaminobenzthiazole; (ii) on heating with aniline it formed triphenylguanidobenzthiazole, and (iii) it could be desulphided with

yellow lead oxide. On a reinvestigation of this work, the above mentioned desulphidation reaction and formation of triphenylguanidobenzthiazole and sulphur could not be confirmed. But considerable formation of carbanilide was observed in addition to the other above-mentioned products. In fact, the two major products of these decompositions were always found to be carbanilide and 2-phenylaminobenzthiazole. It was further found that the base had a hydrogen which was reactive to sodium and it also formed a *N*-nitroso derivative with nitrous acid.

From these facts two conclusions are evident : (i) that the base must be represented by a structure which contains an active NH* group and (ii) on hydrolytic derangement it should easily and primarily provide 2-phenylaminobenzthiazole and carbodiphenylimide. There could not be any reasonable doubt about this last being one of the primary products because it alone would easily (by hydrolysis) form carbanilide which could not be obtained directly from the base as there was no oxygen present in it. Further, it would most easily account for the formation of triphenylguanidine.

It was clear therefore that the thiodiazole structure (I), which did not have any NH group, could not represent Hugershoff's compound. More likely, it is either 2-(triphenylguanido)-benzthiazole (III) or 2-phenylimino-3-diphenylformamidobenzthiazole (IV) (Sahasrabudhey and Suresh, *Proc. Ind. Sci. Cong.*, 1959, Part III, p. 133).

Attempts were made to synthesise Hugershoff's base by condensing (1) 2-chlorobenzthiazole with triphenylguanidine, (2) carbodiphenylimide with 2-phenylaminobenzthiazole and (3) phenyl-mustard oil with triphenylguanidine to afford *N*-phenyl-*N'*-triphenylformamidothiurea and its subsequent oxidation. But we did not succeed in preparing 2-(triphenylguanido)-benzthiazole (identical with III above).

Hofmann and Gabriel's Base

A similar investigation of Hofmann and Gabriel's base (II) has shown that it is incomparably stable when compared to Hugershoff's base. It did not yield a nitroso derivative and was also found unreactive to metallic sodium. Thus, it appears to be a compound of a different type. It has been further found to be identical with the so-called dimethyldiphenylguanidothiurea of Fromm and Baumhauer (*Annalen*, 1908, 361, 324), obtained by the action of methylaniline on methylphenylthiuret.

Since Fromm and Vetter's "phenylguanidophenylthiurea" (*Annalen*, 1907, 366, 180), obtained by a reaction analogous to that of Fromm and Baumhauer (*loc. cit.*), has

*The NH has been further confirmed by infra-red spectral studies. The results will be published in a separate communication.

been shown to be identical with a thiodiazole (Va or Vb), prepared by the oxidative cyclisation of genuine *N*-phenylformamido-*N'*-phenylthiourea, obtained by the condensation of monophenylguanidine carbonate and phenyl-mustard oil (Kurzer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2345; also *B.H.U.J. Sci.*, 1958-59, 9, No. 2), it appears that Hofmann and Gabriel's original thiodiazole structure (II) should hold for their compound.

(Va)

(Vb)

The ultraviolet absorption curves (Fig. 1) of Hofmann and Gabriel's compound

FIG. 1

- Hofmann and Gabriel's thiodiazoles.
- - - Fromm and Vetter's compound
- · - · Oxidation product of *N*-phenylformamido-*N'*-phenylthiourea (Kurzer).

and of Fromm and Vetter's so-called phenylguanidophenylthiourea (in reality identical with Va; *vide infra*) obtained with Beckman D.U. spectrophotometer, are strongly suggestive of the identity of their heteroring systems. The 3:5-positions of substituents in (II) also cannot be doubted as substitution in position-2 is of necessity precluded in the case of Hofmann and Gabriel's compound and the same probably holds good in the case of the thiodiazole derived by oxidation of *N*-phenylformamido-*N'*-phenylthiourea. Thus, of the two likely structures (Va) and (Vb) for this last compound, the former is the more likely one. Kurzer (*loc. cit.*) has assumed the 3:5-diphenylimino-1:2:4-thiodiazole structure for this compound, but has not offered any reason for it.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Hugershoff's Base

Preparation.—To a suspension of thiocarbanilide (15 g.) in cold alcohol (220 c.c.) bromine (5.3 c.c.) in benzene (30 c.c.) was gradually added with stirring. The separated sulphur was removed and the solution basified. A soft base, which hardened on standing, was obtained. It was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 136-37°. (Found: C, 73.14; H, 4.87; N, 13.03; S, 7.38. Calc. for $C_{24}H_{20}N_4S$: C, 74.26; H, 4.79; N, 13.32; S, 7.63%). The compound is not desulphided with alkaline lead acetate. It yielded a picrate, m.p. 161-62°.

Hydrolytic Studies: (a). *With Glacial Acetic Acid*—Hugershoff's base (1 g.) was heated with glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.) for 1 hour. The hydrolysate was diluted when a precipitate, m.p. 147-50°, was thrown down. It was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 158-59°, and identified as 2-phenylaminobenzthiazole by mixed m.p. with an authentic sample. Picrate, m.p. 221-22°.

The filtrate after removing the above residue afforded acetanilide, m.p. 112°, on concentration.

(b). *With 60% Acetic Acid.*—The base (2 g.) was boiled with 60% acetic acid (20 c.c.) for 1 hour. Crystals were obtained on cooling, m.p. 210-28° (0.5 g.). These were recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 233-34° and identified as *NN'*-diphenylcarbamide.

The acidic mother-liquor on keeping furnished crystals of 2-phenylaminobenzthiazole (0.3 g.) which were filtered off and the mother-liquor was diluted when a solid (0.8 g.), m.p. 80-100°, was obtained. It was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 136-37°, and identified as the unchanged base.

A portion of the solid, m.p. 80-100°, on treatment with alcoholic picric acid afforded immediately picrate of 2-phenylaminobenzthiazole, m.p. 222°.

(c). *With HCl (conc.)*.—The base (4 g.) was heated under reflux with HCl (conc., 30 c.c.) for 1½ hours.

(i) On cooling, the residue was filtered and extracted with cold alcohol. The residue left after alcoholic extraction was carbanilide, m.p. 233-34°.

(ii) The alcoholic extract was basified and the base extracted thrice with hot 50% alcohol. Crystals from above 50% alcoholic extract melted at 130-90°. On fractional crystallisation of these, carbanilide (m.p. 237°) and 2-phenylaminobenzthiazole (m.p. 158°) (carbanilide is less soluble) were obtained.

(iii) In the residue left after three extractions, some unchanged original base was isolated by fractional crystallisation from alcohol.

(iv) The acidic filtrate from (i) gave off, on basification, a strong smell of aniline and formed a precipitate of 2-phenylaminobenzthiazole, m.p. 158°. No sulphur could be isolated.

Reaction with Aniline.—Hugershoff's base (4 g.) and aniline (8 c.c.) were heated at 105-10° for an hour and excess aniline was removed by steam distillation. The solid residue, obtained (m.p. 110-20°) on repeated crystallisation from alcohol, melted at 157-58° and was identified as 2-phenylaminobenzthiazole.

The mother-liquor after removing 2-phenylaminobenzthiazole furnished crystals on keeping, m.p. 144°. These were identified with triphenylguanidine by mixed m.p. with an authentic sample.

Pyrolytic Decomposition at 150-60°.—The base (5 g.) was heated at 150-60° for 45 minutes. The melt was extracted with ether; the ethereal solution was evaporated when a solid, m.p. 88-104°, was obtained. The product on two crystallisations from alcohol afforded 2-phenylaminobenzthiazole, which was identified by mixed m.p. with an authentic sample.

The alcoholic mother-liquor after removing the crystals of 2-phenylaminobenzthiazole on dilution gave a product, m.p. 80-100°, which could not be identified.

Nitroso Derivative.—Hugershoff's base was suspended in HCl (dil.) and covered with a layer of benzene. An aqueous solution of sodium nitrite was added gradually in excess with vigorous shaking. The benzene layer was separated, washed twice with water and evaporated under vacuum. Fine yellow crystals, m.p. 72-85°, were obtained. The melting point did not improve on crystallisation. The compound is rather unstable when heated in a solvent. It responded to Libermann's nitroso reaction.

Reaction with Sodium.—Hugershoff's base was dissolved in dry ether and freshly cut pieces of sodium were added. A brisk evolution of hydrogen was noticed and a colorless substance was thrown down, which was the sodium derivative.

Attempts at the Condensation of (i) 2-Chlorobenzthiazole and Triphenylguanidine, (ii) 2-Phenylaminobenzthiazole and Carbodiphenylimide and (iii) Triphenylguanidine and Mustard Oil.—(i) 2-Chlorobenzthiazole (0.5 c.c.) and triphenylguanidine (0.8 g.) were heated at 120-30° for 1 hour. Unchanged chlorobenzthiazole was removed with ether. The residue was proved to be unchanged triphenylguanidine. No other product could be isolated.

(ii) 2-Phenylaminobenzthiazole (2 g.) and thiocarbanilide (2 g.) were heated in presence of lead oxide (6 g.) for 2 hours at 120-30°. A large quantity of 2-phenylaminobenzthiazole along with some low-melting substance was recovered. No other compound could be isolated.

(iii). Triphenylguanidine (5 g.) and phenyl-mustard oil (2.5 c.c.) were heated in alcohol (30 c.c.) for 45 minutes and the solution was filtered. Crystals from alcoholic solution were of triphenylguanidine, indicating that condensation did not take place.

Hofmann and Gabriel's Thiodiazole

Preparation.—*NN*-Methylphenylthiocarbamide (5 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (30 c.c.), slightly warmed and hydrogen peroxide (4 g.) in aqueous solution (70-80 c.c.) was added gradually. An oily product, which solidified on standing, separated along with sulphur. The product was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 93-94°. Picrate m.p. 142° (Sahasrabudhey and Krall, *loc. cit.*). (Found: C, 64.03; H, 5.28; N, 19.64; S, 11.56. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{18}N_4S$: C, 64.8; H, 5.4; N, 19.0; S, 10.8%).

Hydrolytic Studies: (a). *With 60% Acetic Acid*.—Hofmann and Gabriel's base (1 g.) was heated with 60% acetic acid (10 c.c.) for 1½ hours on a water-bath. The solution was cooled and filtered. The residue weighed 0.93 g., m.p. 93-94°. This was identified as unchanged base by mixed m.p. with an authentic sample.

(b). *With HCl (conc.)*.—The base (1 g.) was heated with HCl (conc., 10 c.c.) for 45 minutes under reflux. The solution was filtered and diluted; 0.92 g. of the unchanged base was obtained.

Reaction with Aniline.—The base (1 g.) was heated with aniline (10 c.c.) for 3 hours and the resulting solution was diluted and steam-distilled to remove unchanged aniline. The residue was crystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 93-94°; mixed m.p. with the original base remained undepressed.

Reaction with Nitrous Acid and Sodium.—The base did not react with nitrous acid or metallic sodium, indicating that there was no NH group or active hydrogen in it.

Preparation of the so-called "Dimethyldiphenylguanidothiourea".—Methylphenylthiuret (5 g.) was heated with methylaniline (6.7 c.c.) at 120-25° for 3 hours. The reaction mixture was treated with cold alcohol, filtered to remove sulphur, diluted, basified and steam distilled, when unchanged methylaniline was removed. The residue, a sticky mass, was subjected to prolonged vacuum and cooling, but it did not solidify. It was treated with boiling alcohol and filtered. Some residue, m.p. 158-59°, was left behind which could not be identified. To the alcoholic solution was added alcoholic picric acid and the mixture slightly diluted after removing a sticky mass which had initially separated. A picrate was obtained which after recrystallisation from alcohol melted at 138-39°. No depression in melting point was recorded when mixed with the authentic picrate of Hofmann and Gabriel's base, m.p. 142°.

The picrate on treatment with ammonium hydroxide gave a base, crude m.p. 85-87°. On recrystallisation and mixing with Hofmann and Gabriel's base (m.p. 93-94°), no depression in m.p. was observed.

The same was also obtained by following exactly the procedure of Fromm and Baumhauer (*loc. cit.*) of isolating it, but the yield was poor.

Preparation of Phenylguanidophenylthiourea of Fromm and Vetter.—Phenylthiuret (2.3 g.) and aniline (2 c.c.) in alcohol (30 c.c.) were heated on a boiling water-bath under reflux for 30 minutes. The solution was filtered hot to remove sulphur. Crystals from alcoholic solution were further washed with CS₂ to remove the impurity of sulphur left, if any, and recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 198-200°. The compound was non-desulphidable when treated with hot alkaline lead acetate. (Found: C, 62.41; H, 4.35; N, 21.18; S, 11.95. Calc. for C₁₄H₁₂N₄S: C, 62.68; H, 4.47; N, 20.89; S, 11.94%).

Preparation of 3:5-Diphenylimino- or 2-Phenyl-(3-imino-5-phenylimino)-1:2:4-thiodiazole.—*N*-Phenylformamido-*N'*-phenylthiourea (1 g.) (described in a communication under publication) was dissolved in alcohol (10 c.c.), slightly diluted, acidified with a few drops of HCl and treated with iodine (0.5 g.) in aqueous KI. A crystalline product, m.p. 198-99°, was thrown down. The product was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 198-200°. (Found: C, 62.34; H, 4.58; N, 20.76; S, 11.99. Calc. for C₁₄H₁₂N₄S: C, 62.68; H, 4.47; N, 20.89; S, 11.94%).

This was identified with the above described Fromm and Vetter's compound through comparison of their m.p.s and undepressed mixed m.p.s of the mixtures of substances and their derivatives and through ultraviolet absorption spectra (Fig. 1).

Ultraviolet Absorption Spectra of Fromm and Vetter's, Kurzer's and Hofmann and Gabriel's Compounds

Double or triple crystallised compounds were used. Absolute alcohol was used as solvent and the observations were recorded with a Beckman D.U. spectrophotometer. Concentrations of the solutions in 10 c.c. absolute alcohol were as follows: Hofmann and Gabriel's thiodiazole 0.0001 g., Fromm and Vetter's compound 0.0001 g. and oxidation product of *N*-phenylformamido-*N'*-phenylthiourea (Kurzer) 0.00012 g. The results are represented in Fig. 1.

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